

THE ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

In this article, in the field of protection of the rights of entrepreneurs - the creation of an effective system of support for business entities, especially during the period of establishing their activities, private entrepreneurship in many ways affects the rate of economic growth, it is said that it is one of the leading sectors that determine the state of population employment, the structure and quality of the gross domestic product.

Keywords: economic growth, activity, direction, entrepreneurship, development, business, improvement, measures.

Today, the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev "On measures to fundamentally improve the system of state protection of legal interests of business and further development of entrepreneurship" was announced. According to the text of the decree, to implement the tasks defined in the Action Strategy for the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, to establish effective communication and healthy partnership mechanisms between the business community and state bodies, strengthening guarantees of reliable protection of the rights and legal interests of private ownership and business entities, introducing a permanent channel of current information exchange with entrepreneurs on the issues of improving the business environment, first of all in regions, cities, and districts, supporting entrepreneurial activities-tasks performed in several areas to achieve the practical results of the measures implemented in the field of support, to provide comprehensive assistance to the population in organizing and running their own business, as well as to ensure the provision of high-quality state services to business entities listed. Including:

In the field of protection of the rights of entrepreneurs - to create an effective system of support for business entities, especially during the period of establishing their activities, to strengthen the guarantees of reliable protection of their rights and legal

interests, to provide all-round support for their rapid development, ensuring the priority role and inviolability of private property and entrepreneurship, wide involvement of the population in entrepreneurship activities in the districts and cities of our republic, including:

- analysis of the state of compliance with the rights and legal interests of business entities by competent bodies and presenting its results to the Office of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other competent bodies on a systematic basis;

- introduction of a practical mechanism of public control over the implementation of legislation in the field of business activity, first of all by local state authorities, and preparation of an independent assessment of their activity and submission to the Cabinet of Ministers;

- protection of the interests of business entities that filed complaints against state and economic management bodies, managers and employees of local government bodies;

- several measures were developed, such as monitoring the activities of business entities and ensuring the participation of the members of the Chamber in the inspections of their activities.

The activities of an entrepreneur in his field of activity are multifaceted. It is determined by the change of market policy or the influence of internal and external factors of the enterprise. However, the main goal of an entrepreneur is to make a profit, as well as to carry out activities that ensure efficient operation in the market. To do this, it is necessary to create a mechanism based on modern management methods that support entrepreneurship and ensure its effective use. When managing a business in market conditions, it is necessary to take into account its following features:

- the entrepreneur always works taking into account the demand and supply in the market;

- the entrepreneur makes efforts to ensure efficiency and looks for ways to reduce production costs;

- persons who are responsible for the final results of the business, create sufficient opportunities to conduct their business under free conditions;

- the final results of a small enterprise, i.e. its profit or loss, will be known only in the process of trading in the market;

- an entrepreneur engaged in small business does not know exactly what kind of risk he will face in the market or what the final result will be.

Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, based on independent initiative, responsibility, entrepreneurial idea, profit-oriented, goal-oriented activity.

Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, the initial stage of which is usually associated with thinking activity or its result, only then it takes a material form.

Entrepreneurship is defined by the presence of creativity in the field of introducing innovation, changing the activity of production of goods or organizing an enterprise (including a small enterprise). Creative aspects of entrepreneurial activity are expressed in the implementation of new methods or new technologies of organizing production in a new system of management.

The main goal of the entrepreneur is to determine the need for the product in order to have his customers. An entrepreneur should take into account the following main factors when forming his customers:

- novelty of the product and its compatibility with the buyer;
- quality of goods or services;
- price of goods or services;
- degree of universality of the product;
- appearance of the product, its compatibility with the buyer's requirements;
- the possibility of using after-sales services;
- compliance of the goods with accepted general or state standards;
- attractiveness of advertisement of goods and services, attraction of customer's attention, etc.

Entrepreneur's personal characteristics, abilities, opportunities, and job qualities are the driving force of entrepreneurship. The entrepreneur's work qualities should be based on the following principles:

- first, to find its place in the economic system by analyzing the level of supply of goods and services to the market;
- secondly, the readiness to create a personal production structure;
- thirdly, based on the results of marketing research, making preliminary business calculations;
- fourthly, the ability to direct the leadership in the implementation of the business project;
- fifth, to be the first to implement a new technical and technological idea and to use this idea in practice, to be able to imagine what kind of final result, products or services can be obtained from it.

The role of small business is determined by the classical tasks of solving small business in developed countries. This will develop a healthy competitive environment of the economy, create a strong motivational incentive system for more full use of knowledge, energy skills and hard work of the population, which in turn will lead to more active development of existing material, personnel, organizational and

technological resources. allows you to log out and use them; formation of a quality system of household, organizational and production services; creating a large number of new jobs, forming the most important layer of society, developing the innovative potential of the economy, introducing new forms of organization, production, sales and financing.

The development of small business creates the necessary conditions for rapid economic growth, helps to fill local markets, and at the same time allows to cover the costs of the market economy (unemployment, crisis).

The importance of entrepreneurship is that small businesses compete fiercely for survival and are forced to constantly evolve and adapt to the current market conditions, because in order to exist, you need to get funding to live, that is, to be better than others, better they work for profit.

Private entrepreneurship is one of the leading sectors that largely determines the rate of economic growth, the state of population employment, the structure and quality of the gross domestic product. responds to global trends to form an adequate model of the economy that implements state regulation of medium and small production. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms aimed at protecting the privacy of private property, strengthening its role and place in the economy, and further improving the business environment and business conditions are being implemented consistently and step by step.

The main goal is to create ample conditions and opportunities for entrepreneurs who create additional jobs, produce quality products and make a significant contribution to development. This was also discussed during the open dialogue of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev with entrepreneurs of our country. At the meeting, tasks that should be implemented in order to further support entrepreneurship, eliminate systemic problems, and listen to their opinions and suggestions were discussed.

Undoubtedly, in the following years, entrepreneurs became the real support and locomotive of the economy and reforms. Undoubtedly, it can be said that our fellow entrepreneurs are the creators of the new Uzbekistan. In turn, the state creates all necessary conditions for them.

As the President noted, further expansion of the ranks of businesswomen and young businessmen and their comprehensive support will continue to be one of the priorities of our economic policy. Thus, the aspirations and efforts of Uzbekistan to become one of the strong and developed countries will begin to bear fruit soon.

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